

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Beyene****FIRST NAME: Hailemichael Taye****PROGRAM CODE : DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: Microsoft office 365 Pro Plus on Windows 10

ACADEMIC WRITING FOR IMPACT

1) SUMMARY OF THE MATERIAL STUDIED

This response paper scrutinizes “ACA-401/ACA 401D Coursepack: Period 1” By Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. The coursepack discusses academic writing basics, steps, key considerations, guidelines, and useful tools. The material starts by providing an overview of the purpose, key components, and steps of writing an academic paper. An academic essay aims to “persuade readers of an idea based on evidence,” and it should not only have a thesis statement but also responds to the specific question (EUCLID 2019, 1). Arguments and reasoning based on ‘evidence supporting evidence and information from academic texts or credible sources.’ are another critical distinguishing feature of an academic paper (ibid). According to the coursepack, an academic essay should be composed of introduction, body, and conclusion. Likewise, it suggests some necessary steps to write an academic paper, and it admits that academic writing is not a linear process. Analysis of a research question and establishing a possible thesis is a good starting point. Another critical step is to research the topic at hand, which helps to get knowledge and evidence to enrich and develop the research question or thesis. For this purpose, the use of “credible academic sources for support and evidence” is vital (ibid). Referencing the essay using appropriate styles is detrimental as it affects the acceptability of the work as well as avoids plagiarism. The course pack also discusses how to prevent plagiarism through proper citation. It also has chapters on key considerations when writing an academic paper as well as a literature review. Another essential area the material discusses is the style guide. It states that:

A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent. Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting. In each of these cases, there is a need to ensure that the writing style is consistent and so guidelines are usually published to allow more than one author to

contribute while ensuring that the finished piece does not necessarily carry the personal style of the writer but that of the publication, company or website associated with the writing. For publications or companies with a large number of contributing authors, a style guide is essential if the finished publication is to be coherent and consistent (EUCLID 2019, 24).

Besides the coursepack, Period 1 has two vital videos. The first one gives orientation on the structure, processes, and components of EUCLID courses. Whereas, the second video demonstrates how to draft and format a response paper using EUCLID style guide.

The preceding section gives an overview of the essential points discussed in the coursepack and videos of Period 1. I will provide my reaction to the content and structure of the coursepack as follows.

2) CONTENT

As discussed in the previous section, the coursepack comprises most of the essential topics that are useful for science writing. However, still, there are areas of improvement to make it more comprehensive, rich in content, and impactful. The following are my observations that I discover while reading the coursepack.

First point: Literature review section need to focus on its definition, purpose, key steps, available methods, and vital considerations

As discussed in chapter one of the course pack researching the topic is a critical step in academic writing. I expected that the literature review section to expand on the what, why, and how of the literature search. However, the chapter instead focuses on grammatical and punctuation issues. For instance, the first paragraph of the section start listing the eleven important reminders as follows:

Eleven (11) Important Reminders

1. To join two independent clauses, use a comma followed by a conjunction, a semicolon alone, or a semicolon followed by a sentence modifier
2. Use commas to bracket nonrestrictive phrases, which are not essential to the sentence's meaning
3. Do not use commas to bracket phrases that are essential to a sentence's meaning
4. When beginning a sentence with an introductory phrase or an introductory (dependent) clause, include a comma (EUCLID 2019, 17).

Having a standalone chapter on literature review is commendable given its critical role in academic writing. However, I strongly recommend that the section should describe what literature review is, its purpose, key steps, available methods, and vital considerations while doing a literature review.

Second point: Use proper examples

One of the critical features of an academic essay is it “should include relevant examples” (ibid). Furthermore, the examples should demonstrate the issues under discussion. Nevertheless, in the coursepack, this is not the case in some instances. For instance, in the section of the material that discusses the use of the comma, the document uses the same example to explain different use of the comma. As you can see below, Example 1 and 2 are the same but applied to demonstrate the formal and informal way of using a comma, respectively.

Example 1: My favorite types of sandwiches are peanut butter and jelly, cream cheese, roast beef, and turkey club. (Formal way)

However, some writers find it acceptable to omit the comma before the conjunction.

Example 2: My favorite types of sandwiches are peanut butter and jelly, cream cheese, roast beef, and turkey club. (Modern way)

Therefore, both examples can be considered acceptable. Many teachers and grammar guides instruct that the inclusion of the second comma is optional (EUCLID 2019, 20).

Likewise, the example used in the section that describes “other common usage differences” i.e “(G.B.) He’s in the hospital with a broken leg. (U.S.) He’s in the hospital with a broken leg.” shows a similarity than a difference as both G.B. and U.S sentences are the same (EUCLID 2019, 30).

Third point: There is a critical section missing in the area of scientific publishing

Writing an academic paper is a means, not an end by itself. It should help to communicate, influence, and impact various audiences, including those that are in the academic and scientific world. Publishing is one of the mechanisms to disseminate research results. For this purpose, knowledge of scientific publishing is crucial. Some of the areas this section can cover include how to identify quality journals for publication, the process, and steps from submitting first drafts to review the paper and finally publishing. Furthermore, an annex of the list (and websites) of high impact factor journals in the sustainable development field would also be helpful. Therefore, I strongly recommend the inclusion of the scientific publishing section as it is fundamental for postgraduate students to disseminate their research findings widely.

Fourth point: include more on major referencing styles and on how to do proper citations

The course pack mentioned about the importance of proper citations in several places and gave details of the Chicago style guide. However, I believe that the students should understand all the dominant types of referencing styles as it will help them to publish their research work in different journals. Most journals have their publication guideline

but follow one of the key referencing styles. Hence, I suggest the inclusion of more detailed information on the major citation styles, including their similarities and differences (this could be in a table form).

Chapter 2 provides essential knowledge of plagiarism and citation. Nevertheless, I believe that more work is needed to make the material comprehensive to give enough information about the topic. For example, the format to “list of Works Cited” sections focuses on only one style guide and a couple of publication types such as books and online works (EUCLID 2019, 11). It is not clear how to cite journal articles, conference papers, Ph.D. dissertations, research reports, etc. and how to do citations using American Psychological Association (APA), Modern Language Association (MLA), and Oxford styles, for example.

3) STRUCTURE AND ORGANIZATION

Fifth point: Use of tables, boxes, etc. to improve the readability and clarity of the course pack

Another area of improvement for the course pack is its structure and organization. Based on my observations, some of the sections/subsections are not very clear for the reader due to limitations in structuring and organizing the contents. For instance, chapter 6 has beneficial information that can help the student to understand the differences between American and British English. However, some of the sentences/words/examples are not clear whether they are American or British English. The following example demonstrates what I am trying to explain:

Same Term, Different but Similar Spelling and Pronunciation

Aluminium — aluminum

Polythene — polyethylene

Maths — math (shortening of “mathematics”)

Rise — raise (more money in salary, wages) (EUCLID 2019, 20)

Someone without background knowledge can not identify which is American or British English. It is useful to create tables, figures, diagrams, and separate compare/contrast lists to compare different categories. Specifically, table presentation with three columns (American, British, and remark) would make it more understandable and straightforward. Therefore, I suggest reviewing the structure and organization of the coursepack to improve its clarity and readability.

4) CONCLUSION

Most of my work experience has been in research institutes, which demands writing scientific manuscripts. I have taken not only short courses in scientific writing but also published several articles in renowned journals. Hence, I am familiar with most of the contents discussed in the coursepack. I have been using American Psychological Association (APA) referencing style, and this course has introduced me to Chicago style. The coursepack is useful, especially for students who are new to science writing as it constitutes most of the essential topics such as the purpose, steps, and critical considerations of academic writing, referencing styles, grammar, formatting, and plagiarism. However, as discussed in the previous sections, I firmly believe that there is room for improving the content and structure of the coursepack to make it more useful and appealing. I recommend an extensive literature review preceded the redevelopment of the coursepack.

REFERENCES

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